

Ultra Comm: The Next Generation of Multi-Band, Multi-Mode Communication Systems

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Abstract

This paper describes the Ultra Comm communication system design, and provides details on the numerous advanced technologies that are being brought together by Ultra Comm. Various application scenarios, both military and commercial, are also included.

I. INTRODUCTION

The information environment of the future will require a flexible, low-cost communication system that not only takes advantage of the latest developments in communications technology, but also is interoperable with fielded legacy systems. Unfortunately, military and civil communications systems have become increasingly complex, with dozens of standards, a mixture of analog and digital signal formats, and diverse spectral utilization. Furthermore, diminishing fiscal resources dictate a low-cost solution that can be applied in many different scenarios, both commercial and military, with a minimum of additional engineering costs.

Recently, the Sensor Technology Office of the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA/STO) and the Information Directorate of the Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL/IF) have contracted with Raytheon E-Systems of Falls Church, VA to develop a multi-band, multi-mode communications system that will address the issues identified above, with planned availability in the 4th quarter of 2000. This effort will bring together some of the most powerful and innovative technologies available to develop a system that is flexible, modular, programmable, low power, low cost, and designed to be used in both military and commercial applications. This advanced communication system is known as Ultra Comm – a single, compact system that handles virtually all bands and modulation schemes in a credit card size package.

One Ultra Comm module provides four independent communication channels, with each channel capable of covering the RF communication bands between 20 MHz and 2.8 GHz. The system

can provide up to 60 MHz of instantaneous bandwidth, is low power, and is completely software reconfigurable throughout the spectrum.

II. ULTRA COMM SYSTEM OVERVIEW

The Ultra Comm communications system is based on a family of modular components, packaged in the widely used PC Card format developed by the Personal Computer Memory Card International Association (PCMCIA card). This modularity allows users to maximize the benefits of economies of scale and reduce unit costs by eliminating unneeded functionality. Descriptions of the receive and transmit modules follow.

A. Advanced Digital Receiver

The Ultra Comm Advanced Digital Receiver (ADR) is comprised of several subsystem functions as shown in the conceptual block diagram in Figure 1.

Figure 1. ADR Functional Block Diagram.

These include the radio frequency (RF) preselect filter which selects the signal band of interest and rejects out-of-band signals and interference, the RF downconverter which translates the desired RF frequency band to an intermediate frequency (IF) suitable for digitization, and the analog-to-digital converter (ADC) that samples the analog IF signal and outputs a digital IF signal. The digital subsystem converts the digital IF to baseband and demodulates, processes, and formats the signals of interest. It also provides control interfaces to the RF downconverter for automatic gain control (AGC) and tuning control,

as well as providing interfaces between the digital signal processing (DSP) hardware and software for real-time data and message transfer. An I/O and control function interfaces the ADR with the Small Peripheral Control Interconnect/Interface (SPCI) bus, and a power conditioning subsystem provides regulated and conditioned voltages to highly noise-sensitive circuitry in the ADR from the primary power source. The entire assembly is mechanically designed and packaged as a PCMCIA card. Table 1 provides the key performance specifications for the receiver.

Parameter	Specification
Frequency Range	20-2800 MHz
Rx Channels	4
Instantaneous Bandwidth	60 MHz
Dynamic Range	> 90 dB
Noise Figure	8 dB
Tuning Resolution (Digital)	< 5 Hz
Tuning Speed	< 25 μ s
RF Tuning Step Size	5 MHz nom.
Power Consumption	< 10 W

Table 1. ADR Key Specifications.

Each of the receiver subsystems will now be described in more detail.

RF Preselect Subsystem

A block diagram of the RF preselector is shown in figure 2. The ADR preselector accepts an RF input in the range of 20 MHz to 2.8 GHz, and provides a

Figure 2. RF Preselect Functional Block Diagram.

band-limited RF output at the selected center frequency. Digital control inputs allow selection of

the appropriate filter band, and the external voltages provide actuation and supply voltages for the various components of the subsystem.

Each of the three tunable bandpass filters use impedance and admittance inverters and are designed such that the tuning specifications can be realized using only capacitive tuning, with fixed inductive elements. Both the tunable capacitors and fixed inductors are implemented using novel microelectromechanical (MEM) devices.

MEM capacitors, as used in the Ultra Comm preselector, are essentially a metal membrane suspended above a metal electrode covered with an insulating layer, as shown in figure 3. When the suspended membrane is actuated with electrostatic force, it is deformed downward and comes in contact with the dielectric layer covering the electrode.

Figure 3. MEM Switch/Capacitor Cross-Section.

These two metal plates, separated by a dielectric layer, form a capacitor that has two distinct values, C_{on} and C_{off} . Typically, the ratio of C_{on} to C_{off} is 80-110. Switching occurs in less than 2 μ s, and requires an actuation voltage of 30 - 50 volts. These switchable capacitors are arranged in parallel, binary-weighted banks to fabricate digitally selectable capacitors with up to nine bits of resolution.

MEM device technology is also used to fabricate high-Q fixed inductors for the filters. Shown in figure 4 is a conceptual cross-section of a MEM inductor. A suspended air bridge of metal forms half of one turn of the spiral inductor. The other half turn

Figure 4. MEM Inductor Cross-Section.

lies on the substrate and connects one air bridge to the next. Inductor values of 0.5 - 20 nH over a frequency range of 0.1 - 3 GHz can be achieved. Q values comparable with traditional 3-D filled core and air-core solenoidal coils are expected.

In order to get extremely high performance filtering over the entire Ultra Comm frequency band,

alternatives to the lumped-element filters described above are being considered. Acoustic MEM filtering technology being developed at the University of Michigan has the potential to be a desirable

Figure 5. Acoustic MEM Resonator/Bandpass Filter.

alternative. In figure 5, an acoustic MEM resonator is shown. This structure has a resonant frequency with a very high Q, and thus can be used either to synthesize a particular frequency or act as a bandpass filter. Unfortunately, these devices currently have an upper limit to the frequencies that they can operate at. Until these devices can operate over the full Ultra Comm frequency band, a hybrid approach will be used whereby acoustic devices are used below 200-300 MHz, lumped element devices are used above 800 MHz, and a hybrid lumped-element/acoustic solution is used to cover the intermediate frequencies.

RF Downconverter Subsystem

A single mix RF application-specific integrated circuit (ASIC) constitutes most of the RF Downconverter Subsystem Function. The ASIC receives the band-limited RF signal from the preselector, downconverts the RF signal to an intermediate frequency (IF) in the 565 MHz to 1400 MHz range, and processes the IF signals to be compatible with the input to one of several ADCs.

The RF ASIC will be fabricated in Silicon Germanium (SiGe) technology, which is suitable for combining RF functions and digital functions into one integrated circuit. External frequency synthesis components will be used to generate the external reference and optional local oscillator (LO) signals. These external components will be implemented using the newer acoustic MEM resonator technology discussed in the last section and shown in figure 5. As stated earlier, this structure has a resonant frequency with a very high Q, and thus can be used either to synthesize a particular frequency or act as a bandpass filter. For the frequency synthesis role, arrays of these devices will be fabricated, each with a particular resonant frequency. Digital control logic would then be used to select the frequency of interest.

Analog-to-Digital Converter Subsystem

The ADC subsystem utilizes four channels, converting at a rate of 65 million samples per second (MSPS), to supply data to the digital subsystem. The ADC currently selected is a commercially available Analog Devices AD6640, a 12-bit converter capable of sampling at 65 MSPS with an input bandwidth of 0 - 300 MHz. The modular packaging technique for the ADC will allow a variety of ADC types to be used as they become available or as requirements change.

Digital Subsystem

The digital subsystem is a high-speed signal processing function that includes a signal processing element, based on the Texas Instruments (TI) C62 digital signal processor (DSP) and an SPCI input/output (I/O) control element. The direct down converter (DDC) receives the four channel inputs from the ADC and passes the channelized data streams to the high performance DSP, which operates at 1600 million instruction per second (MIPS). The data is demodulated and passed to the host computer over the SPCI bus. The digital subsystem is supported by a field programmable gate array (FPGA) used to interface to the controlling host computer, RF pre-selector, RF subsystem, and DDC.

Power Conditioning Subsystem

The power conditioning subsystem provides the power distribution to the ADR. It removes transients, and provides regulated voltage levels as required by the other ADR functions to meet performance specifications. The power conditioner also isolates analog and digital power loops, provides electromagnetic noise filtering for all devices, and assures sufficient grounding of all circuits in the ADR.

Software Subsystem

The receiver's software subsystem automatically performs all processor initializations upon power up, and loads the software required to meet all of the receiver requirements. Additionally, the software subsystem performs the final demodulation of the waveform. Initial waveform capabilities for the Ultra Comm receiver are expected to be U.S. cellular and SINCGARS. Due to the complete re-programmability of the Ultra Comm system, additional waveforms may be added by modifying only the software subsystem.

B. Advanced Digital Transmitter

A functional block diagram of the Ultra Comm transmit module is shown in figure 6. The transmit modules provide up to 30 W of output power over the complete Ultra Comm frequency range of 20 MHz to 2.8 GHz. Packaging of the transmit modules is

Figure 6. Transmitter Functional Block Diagram.

accomplished using two PCMCIA cards, one for an exciter module and another for the power amplifier (PA) module.

Exciter Module

The exciter module provides a programmable output signal with 0.1 W to 4 W of power. It receives the I/Q modulation data, clock, LO, and control signals from the ADR. The direct digital synthesis (DDS) function converts the digital modulation data to an analog offset baseband modulated waveform using a digital upconverter (DUC) and a digital-to-analog converter (DAC). The LO upconverts the signal which is then filtered by a MEM filter to reject the LO and mixer components. A pre-amplifier then boosts the signal to 4 W and it is sent to the PA module.

Power Amplifier Module

The PA module receives the 4 W pre-amplified signal from the exciter module and performs final amplification and output matching functions. Amplification is done using a Silicon Carbide (SiC)-based amplifier. SiC has the benefit of being able to operate efficiently at very high junction temperatures. High reliability can be achieved with a SiC PA operating at 300°C junction temperature. At this temperature, the PA can deliver 30-40 W to the matching network at 40-45% efficiency.

To insure maximum power transfer to the antenna, the signal generated by the PA must be carefully matched on the output. Load mismatches result in inefficiency caused by signal power being converted to heat. Unlike traditional matching networks, which are usually efficient over a narrow

range of frequencies, the Ultra Comm PA module provides efficient power transfer over a wide frequency range by using novel MEM matching networks. These MEM-based networks are unique because they can cover the entire frequency range, handle the high power generated by the PA, and still be small enough to fit in the PC card. The MEM-based impedance matching networks will use fixed MEM inductors and tunable MEM capacitors much like those in the preselect filter of the ADR.

III. APPLICATION SCENARIOS

The flexibility of this small, low-cost, multi-band, multi-mode software reprogrammable radio make it inherently useful for many applications. When the same family of devices is used on many platforms and in many applications, interoperability becomes less difficult to achieve.

There are many potential applications for the Ultra Comm family of modules, including airborne and mobile platforms, commercial wireless products, (both base station and mobile), personal communication systems (PCS), and commercial/private aircraft communications.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

An overview of the Ultra Comm communication system has been presented. The receiver and transmitter modules have been described, and each of the advanced technologies contributing to the ambitious Ultra Comm specifications have been discussed. Finally, various application scenarios have been proposed.

While Ultra Comm itself represents a huge step forward in small, low-cost, programmable communication systems, it is only one step in the evolution towards the ultimate goal of a single-chip multi-band, multi-mode software reprogrammable communications device. Many of the technologies brought together and demonstrated by Ultra Comm will be instrumental in achieving this goal.

V. REFERENCES

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